

From

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SECRETARY

THE BRITISH ACADEMY

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Dear Mr. Williamson,

Thank you for letting us know where matters stand over the Sirjan excavation. From the Academy's point of view the award towards the cost of this excavation is valid for two years, but I hope that you are successful in securing a permit for excavation this coming March. If this is not forthcoming, we should be glad if you would keep us informed of developments, as well as of your own plans. Stronach will, I believe, be over here in November, and I will discuss with him what should be done. Meanwhile, I am glad that you are using your time usefully.

Yours sincerely,

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